

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

EMBEDDING ASSESSMENT INTO CLASSROOM ACTIVITIES TO ENHANCE LEARNING OPPORTUNITIES

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Abstract

Embedding assessment into classroom activities is a powerful way to enhance learning opportunities because it provides immediate feedback to both teachers and students, allowing for adjustments in teaching and learning strategies. Teachers can do it effectively by setting clear learning objectives and integrating a variety of formative assessment techniques into their classes. The present article summarizes the assessment practices employed in the process of English teachers training at Pedagogical Institute of Akhmet Baitursynuly Regional University in Kostanay, Kazakhstan. The materials presented here are original and gathered by the authors during 2023-2024 academic year in such English teaching disciplines as General English, English for Special Purposes, English Practical Grammar and Phonetics and English Lexicology Studies.

Keywords: assessment practices, formative and summative assessment, Washback, assessment principles, assessment for learning, assessment of learning, assessment design, test preparation practices.

Introduction: academic background

The professional preparation of prospective English educators at Akhmet Baitursynuly Regional University, Pedagogical Institute after Umyrzak Sultangazin, Kazakhstan, constitutes an integral component of the country's professional training framework, adhering closely to established protocols and guidelines. This process entails a comprehensive four-year regimen at the Bachelor level, culminating in the National Professional Test. [9, 68] Upon completion, individuals are presented with the option to pursue advanced studies through postgraduate programs or commence their careers while engaging in further professional development initiatives. Each academic institution formulates bespoke educational curricula for distinct specializations, subjecting them to rigorous independent evaluation and state endorsement prior to implementation. Notably, the educational program designated as 6B01705 "Foreign Language: Two Foreign Languages", inherits a longstanding legacy in English teacher preparation, tracing its roots back to 1966 within the annals of Kostanay Pedagogical Institute's establishment commemorating the 50th anniversary of the USSR. This esteemed program has yielded a cohort of distinguished graduates, many of whom have made significant contributions to the advancement of foreign language instruction within independent Kazakhstan. Embracing the imperatives of contemporary educational paradigms, the curriculum of this program remains fluid, adapting to evolving exigencies and incorporating cutting-edge pedagogical methodologies.[10] Within this context, Umyrzak Sultangazin Pedagogical

Institute demonstrates unwavering commitment to the integration of the latest instructional techniques in the training of future educators, including English language specialists, among its portfolio of 22 specialized disciplines. A notable component of the professional development framework is the repertoire of assessment procedures, recognized as instrumental in nurturing the professional acumen of participants, facilitating the acquisition of experimental research proficiencies, and fostering the practical application of theoretical constructs gleaned from university courses integrated into the prescribed curriculum. Similar educational procedures are found all over Asia. [4]

The primary methodologies utilized in the current study comprise scientific analysis and synthesis, description, discussion, lesson modeling, observation, and questionnaire administration.

The issue of assessment has been always discussed in the field of language education. "The knowledge, skill and abilities required to design, maintain or evaluate, large scale standardized and/or classroom based tests, familiarity with test processes, and awareness of principles and concepts that guide and underpin practice, including ethics and codes of practice." [6,125]. Starting our research we asked ourselves: What is Assessment Literacy? How can it be fostered in teachers? Assessment literacy refers to the understanding, knowledge, and skills that teachers need to effectively design, implement, and interpret assessments to support student learning. It involves knowing how to create assessments that are valid, reliable, and fair, as well as

being able to use assessment data to inform instructional decisions and improve teaching practices. [8, 112] Fostering assessment literacy in teachers is crucial for ensuring that assessments serve their intended purpose of enhancing learning opportunities for students. [7] Some ways to promote assessment literacy [14, 3] among teachers include professional development, modeling lessons with assessment procedures embedded in them, collaborative learning communities, feedback and coaching, resources and tools, reflective practice applied to both teaching and learning.

Professional development offered as an ongoing opportunity focused on assessment literacy including workshops, seminars, and courses covers topics such as assessment design, item writing, rubric development, and data analysis techniques. [6] We model effective assessment practices in teacher training sessions and staff meetings. Demonstrations how to create clear learning objectives, develop assessment tasks aligned with those objectives, and provide meaningful feedback to students work best. Collaborative learning communities emerge when teachers are encouraged to collaborate and share best practices related to assessment. Peer observation, lesson study groups, and collaborative planning sessions provide opportunities for us, as teachers, to learn from each other and refine their assessment skills. [1, 56] Feedback and coaching plays an important role in providing constructive feedback and coaching to teachers of the Foreign Languages Department on their assessment practices. This is done through classroom observations, one-on-one meetings, or peer coaching arrangements where teachers support each other in improving their assessment techniques. Resources and tools provided to the teachers with access to resources and tools that support assessment literacy, such as assessment guides, rubric templates, and assessment software platforms enhance progressive development of the assessment procedures employed at our Department. These resources help teachers develop their understanding of assessment principles and streamline the assessment process. [8] Such understanding gets its reinforcement through reflective practice when teachers are encouraged to engage in reflective practice regarding their assessment strategies, especially in the periods of intermittent and term assessments. Modern technologies of education give us multiple opportunities for including such resources as Google docs, AI assistance and Videoconferencing for such purposes. [13, 114] Encouraging them to critically examine the effectiveness of their assessments, consider alternative approaches, and continuously seek ways to improve the Chairperson of the Foreign Languages Department creates productive collaborative atmosphere which helps teachers in doing their jobs as well as students who receive better educational service. Assessment is embedded in Teacher Education Programs: it ensures that assessment literacy is integrated into teacher training and students learn about innovative teaching practices through learning with them in their education programs. Pre-service teachers should have opportunities to learn about assessment theory and practice, as well as gain hands-on experience with de-

signing and implementing assessments in real classroom settings – it brings theory close to real life and assessment practices. By promoting assessment literacy among teachers through these strategies, we, educators enhance the quality of assessments used in the classroom, ultimately leading to improved student learning outcomes. [5] We Integrate formative assessment techniques throughout the lesson, thus making assessment a part of learning. It helps overcome student anxiety related to testing: “The word test can make people nervous. It has semantic qualities that make us think of being judged or measured by someone or something.” [14,2]

Varied assessment methods are applied to future teacher training at Pedagogical Institute of Akhmet Baitursynuly Regional University in Kostanay, Kazakhstan. Innovative pedagogy allows creating a whole ecosystem in educational sphere that through effective management of online and offline tools leads to better results in students' performance. [2] In such English teaching disciplines as General English, English for Special Purposes, English Practical Grammar and Phonetics and English Lexicology Studies we use a variety of assessment methods to accommodate different learning styles and preferences. This includes written assignments, oral presentations, group projects, quizzes, debates, and multimedia presentations. Oral projects and assignments develop students' intercultural competence and leads them to deeper comprehend subtle nuances of the target language, such as irony. [3]

The methods employed for formative assessment include:

Think-Pair-Share: Students think about a question or prompt individually, discuss it with a partner, and then share their thoughts with the class.

Exit Tickets: Brief questions or tasks students complete at the end of the lesson to demonstrate their understanding.

Peer Assessment: Students assess each other's work or participation, promoting collaboration and self-reflection.

Self-Assessment: Encourage students to reflect on their own learning progress and set goals for improvement.

Authentic Tasks are designed as assessments that mimic real-world tasks or scenarios relevant to students' lives. This increases engagement and motivation while assessing their ability to apply knowledge and skills in practical contexts. It is crucial to provide timely feedback as this is the essential feature leading students in their educational effort. Providing prompt and constructive feedback to students on their performance which should be specific, focused on the learning objectives, and include suggestions for improvement minimizes stress and anxiety in the learning environment. Very often adjustments in teaching are required when the assessment data informs our teaching practices. Identifying areas where students are struggling and adjusting instruction accordingly involves revisiting certain concepts, providing additional resources, or offering differentiated instruction to meet individual student needs.

Test Purpose refers to the reason why the test is being administered and what it aims to measure. It provides clarity on the intended outcomes of the assessment. For example a language proficiency test may be designed to assess students' ability to communicate effectively in a target language, while a placement test may be intended to determine students' readiness for a particular level of instruction. Norm and criterion referenced testing is distinguished in the teacher training process. Norm-referenced testing compares an individual's performance against the performance of a group (norm) and ranks individuals relative to each other. Standardized tests like the SAT or GRE use norm-referenced scoring, where test-takers' scores are compared to those of a larger population to determine percentiles or rankings. While criterion-referenced testing evaluates an individual's performance against a predetermined standard or criterion. A driving test is a criterion-referenced assessment where individuals must demonstrate specific skills and knowledge to pass the test and obtain a driver's license.

Validity and reliability are integral features of every test. Validity refers to the extent to which a test measures what it intends to measure. It ensures that the inferences drawn from test scores are accurate and meaningful. A reading comprehension test is valid if it accurately assesses students' ability to comprehend written texts. Reliability refers to the consistency and stability of test scores over time and across different administrations. It ensures that test scores are dependable and free from random error. A reliable test will produce consistent results when administered to the same group of students under similar conditions on different occasions. Washback and Test Fairness are the troublesome issues that are often worrying both teachers and students. Washback, also known as backwash or the testing effect, refers to the impact of testing on teaching and learning. It examines how the results of an assessment influence instructional practices and student learning behaviors. High-stakes standardized tests may lead to teaching strategies focused solely on test preparation, neglecting other important aspects of the curriculum. Test fairness ensures that all test-takers have an equal opportunity to demonstrate their knowledge and skills, regardless of their background or characteristics. Providing accommodations such as extra time or alternative formats for students with disabilities ensures test fairness by removing barriers to performance.

Recommendations for achievable best practice that have been developed at the Foreign Languages Department include the following ideas:

- **Clear Alignment:** Ensure that test content, format, and scoring criteria align closely with the test purpose and intended learning outcomes.
- **Diverse Assessment Methods:** Use a variety of assessment methods to capture different aspects of students' knowledge and skills.
- **Validity and Reliability Checks:** Conduct validity and reliability analyses to ensure the accuracy and consistency of test scores.
- **Fairness Considerations:** Address potential sources of bias and discrimination in test design and administration to promote fairness for all test-takers.

- **Transparent Communication:** Provide clear instructions and expectations to test-takers regarding the purpose, format, and scoring of the test to minimize anxiety and maximize performance.

By understanding and applying these important test concepts, educators can develop assessments that effectively measure student learning and contribute to meaningful educational outcomes. Opportunities for reflection, when built in the lesson models give a chance for students to reflect on their learning experiences. This can be done through class discussions, written reflections, or portfolio assessments where students compile evidence of their learning progress over time.

By embedding assessment into classroom activities in these ways, teachers can create a more dynamic and effective learning environment where students are actively engaged, motivated to learn, and supported in their academic growth. Test preparation involves explicit instruction on test content, format, and scoring criteria, along with practice exercises and mock tests to simulate testing conditions. Students engage in self-study, review sessions, and peer collaboration to reinforce learning and build confidence in their test-taking abilities. Test preparation courses, tutoring services, and online resources offer additional support to help students navigate the demands of standardized tests and optimize their performance.

Overall, washback from assessment practices exerts a significant influence on materials development, course design, teaching and learning practices, and test preparation strategies in language education. It underscores the interconnectedness between assessment and instruction, highlighting the importance of aligning assessment practices with educational goals and fostering meaningful learning experiences for students.

Conclusion

The outcomes of this investigation encompass the advancement of future English teacher professional competence and the practical application of diverse assessment methodologies in English language instruction, resulting in the enhancement of the educational process and the development of fundamental foreign language proficiencies among student participants. The conclusions drawn from this research elucidate how the organization of assessment practices contributes to the professional development of prospective English educators and elucidate the impact of integrating testing for learning on the educational process, delineating both its positive and negative ramifications. The materials employed in this study are original and were derived from the professional training of aspiring English teachers scheduled for graduation in June 2024 and June 2025 from the aforementioned university. Following successful completion of the National Teachers Professional Testing, it is anticipated that they will secure teaching positions in Kazakhstan. Subsequent research endeavors are intended to implement the findings of this phase into the pre-service professional training of English teachers, with the ensuing results slated for dissemination in professional journals and conferences.

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